

DESIGN OF BOLTED JOINTS FOR COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

Graphite fiber reinforced polymeric composites have been used extensively in the primary and secondary structures of modern military and civilian aircraft. In these structures, bolted joints are important considerations in structural design and repair. Most of the current design methods have been developed for single fastener joints. In general, design optimization is not available. This paper describes an analytical method for optimizing the design of multi-fastener composite joints. The results of the application of the method in a parametric investigation into the effects of design variables on the failure modes and joint strength are presented. Future development of the method for bolted patch repair of composite structures is discussed.

INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced polymeric composites are ideal for aerospace application because their superior strength-to-weight and stiffness-to-weight ratios enable engineers to meet weight saving targets without compromising structural performance. A complete aircraft structure, for example, is manufactured from many different parts such as skins, stiffeners, frames, spars, etc. These parts must be assembled to form components and then finally the whole structure. Adhesive bonding and mechanical fastening are the joining methods used in the assembly of parts made from thermoset composites. Although adhesive bonding has many advantages including higher joint efficiency and lower part counts, mechanically fastened joints are indispensable because manufacturing breaks are required for disassembly, inspection, repair or replacement. Since the joints are a major source of stress concentration, they are perhaps the most prone to failure. Because of the material's anisotropic behaviour, poor yielding capability, and the absence of fiber reinforcement in the through-the-thickness direction, the failure modes are, in general, very different from those of a metallic joint. As a result, design methods for metallic joints cannot be applied directly in composite joints. This concern has prompted extensive engineering effort in developing appropriate design methods for mechanically fastened composite joints. The state-of-the-art design methods employed are based on finite element methods, two dimensional theory of elasticity, and boundary collocation methods. Most of the methods have been developed for the design of single fastener joints. In general, design optimization is not available. The authors have developed an analytical method based on a complex variational approach for joint design optimization [1]. In this paper, the result of the application of the method in the selection of design parameters for optimizing the joint strength is presented. Future development of the method for bolted patch repair of composite structures is discussed.

DESIGN OPTIMIZATION

An analytical model has been developed for optimizing the design of multiple fastener composite joints. This model consists of three parts: (i) stress analysis, (ii) strength prediction, and (iii) optimization of strength. A flowchart illustrating the major stages in joint strength optimization is shown in Fig. 1. The model has been incorporated into a computer code which enables joint design to be optimized on a personal computer.

The first stage is to identify whether the type of joint to be used in the structure is single-lap or double-lap. These configurations consist of two plates for the single-lap joint or three plates for the double-lap joint connected by two or more fasteners. The plate material can be composite or metal. The plates are of the same finite width, W , and have, in general, m circular or elliptical holes of various sizes which are arbitrarily located in the plate as shown in Fig. 2. The load, P , applied at the end of a plate is in equilibrium with the m fastener loads, P_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, m$). The model assumes that the load on one plate is transferred by flexible frictionless fasteners over half of the hole edge and the secondary bending of the plate in the single-lap configuration is negligible compared to the in-plane deformation. The fasteners are modeled as elastic beams, as shown in Fig. 3, with both ends fixed for the double-lap joint. For the single-lap joint, the fasteners are fixed at one end and are free to translate in the loading direction at the other end, see Fig. 3. In this way, the rotation of fasteners is simulated.

The next stage is joint stress analysis which takes into account the flexibility of the plates and fasteners. In order to determine the stress state in the joint, the fastener loads must be known. The model uses an iterative scheme, see Fig. 1, to determine the fastener loads for joint stress analysis. In single-lap joints, the applied load at the end of one plate (identified in the model as Plate 2) is transferred by fasteners which are loaded in shear to the other plate (identified as Plate 1) which is fixed at one end. In double-lap joints, the applied load at the end of the middle plate (identified as Plate 2) is transferred to two identical side plates (identified as Plates 1 and 3) which are both fixed at one end. Since the side plates are assumed to be identical, the load is evenly distributed between them and as a result, only Plate 1 is used in the analysis for the double-lap configuration. The iterative scheme involves the following steps:

1. Assign an initial value for each fastener load based on the bending stiffness, EI , of the fastener.
2. Perform a two dimensional stress analysis on Plate 1 using the displacement-based complex variational formulation [2]. The analysis involves only force boundary conditions. The fastener loads, which are obtained from step 1, are simulated by a cosine function. In this step, the hole elongations under the fastener loads and by-pass loads are calculated.
3. Calculate the deflections of the fasteners under the shear loads using the mechanics of materials approach.
4. Calculate the summation of hole elongations and fastener deflections in Plate 1 and use the combined displacement as the rigid body movement of the contact region of the corresponding fastener holes in Plate 2; perform a two dimensional stress analysis of Plate 2. Since the analysis involves both displacement and force boundary conditions, a mixed variational formulation is required [2]. In this step, the reaction forces at the fastener holes in Plate 2 under the rigid body displacements and the applied load are calculated.
5. Use the reaction forces on holes of Plate 2 as new fastener loads and repeat steps 2 to 4 until the solution converges.

In this iterative scheme, the joint stress analysis is performed based on fastener loads which are calculated rather than assumed. The complex variational formulations are beyond the scope of the present paper and can be found in Reference 2.

Following the stress analysis, joint strengths and failure modes are predicted by applying failure criteria. There are many existing failure criteria as indicated in a critical review by Rowlands [3]. In this model, the point stress criterion and the quadratic tensor polynomial criterion [3] are used to predict laminate failure instead of first-ply failure. In order to account for the nonlinear behaviour at

Figure 1. Optimization Model for Bolted Composite Joint Design

Figure 2. Composite Plate Containing Fastener Holes

Figure 3. Fastener Models for Single-Lap and Double-Lap Joints

the hole edge, a set of characteristic lines arranged in a rectangular pattern around the loaded half of the fastener hole is used [2]. In this model, the joint strength is predicted based on elastic stresses determined along the characteristic lines and the failure modes are identified according to the failure locations on the lines. The present model can predict three failure modes which are net-tension, shear-out and bearing.

The joint strength is influenced by many parameters which can be broadly divided into two categories: (a) laminate construction, and (b) joint geometry. In the category of laminate construction, parameters such as material system and layup have significant effects on joint strength and failure mode. In the category of joint geometry, laminate thickness, hole diameter, pitch distance, edge distance, number of fasteners and hole pattern are important parameters. The optimization of joint strength with respect to these design parameters is carried out in two steps. In the first step, the joint strength is maximized with respect to a set of material systems and layups. The joint geometry is held constant. In the second step, the joint strength is optimized with respect to a set of geometric parameters using the optimized material and layup for the laminate. The optimization algorithm proceeds on a one-by-one basis among the candidate configurations until the maximum joint strength is determined.

PARAMETRIC JOINT DESIGN

In the design of bolted composite joints, it is important to consider the effects of the laminate and geometric parameters on the joint strength and failure mode. A design study has been performed to illustrate the application of the model in the selection of parameters for optimizing the joint strength. A composite-to-metal joint, with the configuration shown in Fig. 4, has been used in this study. The composite and metal used in the joint are AS1/3501-6 and aluminium respectively. In the first stage, the model optimizes the layup based on the configuration shown in Fig. 4. Three layups, which are $[45/0/-45/0_3/90/0_3]_s$, $[(45/0/-45/0)_2/0/90]_s$ and $[45/0/-45/0/45/90/-45/0/45/-45]_s$, have been investigated. The result of the optimization has shown that the layup $[(45/0/-45/0)_2/0/90]_s$, which contains 50%, 40% and 10% of 0° , 45° and 90° fibers respectively, yields the highest strength among the three layups.

In the second stage, the model optimizes the joint configuration for the $[(45/0/-45/0)_2/0/90]_s$ laminate. Both the hole diameter, d , and the edge distance, e , vary over a range of values in this study. The distance between the first and second row of fasteners, s_1 , is equal to twice the edge distance. The pitch distance, s_w , is constant and is equal to 3.8 cm. A multivariate constrained optimization scheme is conducted among the ranges of d and e . The failure strength surface and the optimum joint design are shown in Fig. 5. It is noted that the failure strength of the joint varies significantly with d , while it is relatively stable over the range for e .

Geometry: $d = 0.8$ cm, $w/d = 10$, $e/d = 3$, $s/d = 4$, $t_1 = 0.8$ cm, $t_2 = 0.3$ cm

Figure 4. Joint Configuration for Optimization Design

Figure 5. Failure Strength as a Function of d and e

BOLTED PATCH REPAIR APPLICATION

The advent of composite materials in primary load bearing structure of military and civilian aircraft has brought new challenges in structural repair. The principal technique in repair is to attach a patch over the damaged area. The patch can be attached using an adhesive bonding technique. This technique requires controlled repair material storage, specialized surface preparation and extended cure times. As a result, adhesive bonding is usually used for depot repair which produces a permanent repair to the damaged part. In the case of military aircraft used during combat, battle damage repair is usually performed without sophisticated facilities. In order to minimize downtime of the aircraft, the repair is carried out under severe time constraint and the repair is temporary. In addition, adhesive bonding repair for thick part requires scarf or stepped-lap joint configurations. These complicated joint configurations cannot be produced under field conditions. Because of these limitations, the adhesive bonding technique is seldom used in aircraft battle damage repair (ABDR).

The preferred ABDR technique involves the attachment of a metallic patch over the damaged area using "blind fasteners" which can be installed from the outside of the damaged part. A schematic illustration of a bolted patch repair is shown in Fig. 6. Since the bolted patch repair scheme is similar to a single-lap bolted joint, the optimization module has the potential of being used as a design tool for ABDR. However, the optimization module requires further development before it can be applied. The reason is that the bolted patch repair scenario involves damage which can be simulated as an elliptical hole, as shown in Fig. 6, while in the bolted joint design case such a hole is not present. In the bolted patch repair case of an aircraft wing containing projectile impact damage, for example, single shear

aluminum or titanium patches are attached by multiple rows of relatively slender blind fasteners; the patch takes all the skin loads of the cleaned damage hole and so the fasteners on the patch and hole edges take high bearing loads. Multiple external loads are imposed on the wing and so the loads in the skin under the patch are not simple uniaxial but are significantly biaxial. Under the biaxial loading condition and in the presence of the randomly oriented elliptical hole, the fastener loading directions and fastener load distributions at the fastener holes are, in general, not known and cannot be assumed. In order to determine both the fastener load distribution and loading direction, the iterative scheme shown in Fig. 1 must be modified such that complex variational formulation will include the deformation characteristics of a notched plate subjected to biaxial loading. In addition, biaxial failure criteria are required for successful predictions of joint strength and failure mode.

A finite element model, shown in Fig. 7, has been developed for the stress analysis of a bolted patch repair. The objective is to obtain the deformation characteristics and the stress distribution of a bolted patch repair subjected to uniaxial loading. These finite element results can be used to aid the further development of the optimization module. In the finite element model, 3-D shell elements were used in the metallic patch and the composite plate. The fasteners were modelled using beam elements. A layer of 3-D gap elements was used between the fastener and the hole. The material used in the composite plate was AS4/3501-6 and the layup was $[45/0/-45/90]_{6s}$. A series of finite element analyses has been performed. In the first case, the composite plate containing an elliptical hole was analysed. Subsequent cases involved analyses of a titanium patch bolted on the composite plate using 20, 24 and 28 fasteners. The stress distribution of the composite plate without the patch and that with the bolted patch are shown in Figs. 8 and 9 respectively. The stress concentration factor, K_t , defined as the localized stress at the edge of the elliptical hole normalized by the far-field stress, has a maximum value of 4.7 for the case shown in Fig. 8. The bolted patch repair has been shown to be effective in reducing the maximum K_t at the edge of the elliptical hole from 4.7 to 3.9, 2.6 and 2.5 for the 20-, 24- and 28-fastener repair plan respectively. Although the number of finite element analysis cases is limited, it may be concluded that the reduction in the stress concentration factor is diminishing; as a result, further addition of fasteners beyond the 28-fastener case may not produce significant beneficial effects. As shown by the gaps between the fasteners and the holes in Fig. 9, the loading direction of

Geometry: $W_p = 17.8$ cm, $W_T = 15.2$ cm, $e = 1.3$ cm, $p = 2.5$ cm, $d = 0.6$ cm, $a = 10.2$ cm, $b = 5.1$ cm

Figure 6. Bolted Patch Repair of a Laminate Containing an Elliptical Hole

the fasteners, in general, is not parallel to the uniaxial loading direction. This observation helps to reinforce the view that the optimization module must be modified for the bolted patch repair case. The finite element analyses took about 60 hours of CPU time for each case to complete when executed on the Silicon Graphics Challenge L server. As a result, finite element analysis is not a suitable method for field repair application. Since field engineers use personal computers for repair design, the availability of the modified optimization module is essential.

Figure 7. Finite Element Model for Stress Analysis of Bolted Patch Repair

Figure 8. Stress Contours in Composite Plate Containing an Elliptical Hole

Figure 9. Stress Contours in Composite Plate with Bolted Patch Repair (Zoom View)

CONCLUSIONS

An analytical model has been developed for optimization of multi-fastener composite joint design. Algorithms for stress analysis, strength prediction and optimization have been coded in a computer program which can be executed efficiently on a personal computer. Since closed form solutions are used, the burden of mesh regeneration for a new design, as needed in a finite element analysis, is not required. As a result, the model has a high potential for use in ABDR applications. Further work is required in modifying the complex variational formulations to account for the deformation characteristics of a notched plate with a bolted patch under biaxial loads and in constructing a new iterative scheme to determine the fastener load distribution and contact region. In addition, development of suitable biaxial failure criteria is required for bolted patch repair design.

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